

Ultrasonic Velocity Measurements of DDT Solutions in Organic Solvents

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Ultrasonic velocity of DDT solutions in benzene, butan-1-ol and acetone has been measured at different temperatures (35–50°). The adiabatic compressibility, apparent molal compressibility, intermolecular free length, acoustic impedance, molar sound velocity, molar sound compressibility and solvation number of these solutions have been evaluated. The ultrasonic velocity is found to vary in the order, acetone < butan-1-ol < benzene. The values of acoustic impedance, intermolecular free length and solvation number decrease whereas other calculated parameters increase with the increase in temperature.

DDT is a serious environmental contaminant such as in human body tissues¹⁻³, food⁴, water⁵ and pharmaceutical products⁶, as it is highly toxic. In order to study the photodegradation of DDT in organic solvents, it is essential to have a comprehensive knowledge of its physical properties so as to reduce the environmental burden of DDT. The literature survey reveals that the references on ultrasonic velocity measurements are not available, although this technique gives a clear insight of the behaviour of this substance. In our previous communication, we reported the ultrasonic velocity⁷ and other physical properties⁸ of organochloro pesticides, viz. DDT, BHC and endosulphan in methanol. In the present paper, ultrasonic velocity of DDT solutions has been measured in benzene, butan-1-ol and acetone with a view to study the behaviour of DDT in different types of solvents and to calculate several allied parameters.

Experimental

The *pp'*-DDT (technical grade, Hindustan Insecticides Ltd.) was recrystallised in methanol and dried in an air-oven (50°). The purity of *pp'*-DDT was confirmed by m.p. (108–10°) measurement. The organic solvents, viz. benzene, butan-1-ol and acetone (all AnalaR) were purified by distillation and the purity was confirmed by b.p. measurements (benzene, 80°; butan-1-ol, 116–17°; acetone, 65°).

Density was measured at constant temperature with a dilatometer constructed of pyrex glass having a reservoir volume of 15 cm³. The measuring section was constructed of precisely-bored graduated capillary. The uncertainty in density measurements is $\pm 0.01 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$.

Ultrasonic velocity of pesticide solutions was measured with the help of a single crystal ultrasonic interferometer (Mittal Enterprises, India) working at a fixed frequency of 2 MHz. Water from a ther-

mostat maintained at the desired temperature and controlled upto $\pm 0.05^\circ$ was passed through the jacket of the cell before the measurement. The measured velocities have an uncertainty of $\pm 0.5 \text{ ms}^{-1}$.

Results and Discussion

Ultrasonic velocity (*C*) of *p,p'*-Dichloro Diphenyl Trichloroethane (DDT) solutions increases with increase in concentration of the pesticide (Table 1) but decreases with increase in temperature (Fig. 1). However, the values of *C* of DDT solution in different solvent vary in the order, acetone < butan-1-ol < benzene.

Fig. 1. Plots of ultrasonic velocity concentration of DDT solutions in butan-1-ol at different temperatures.

TABLE 1—ULTRASONIC VELOCITY AND OTHER RELATED PARAMETERS FOR DDT AT 308 K IN ORGANIC SOLVENTS

Concn. mol dm ⁻³	Density × 10 ⁻³ kg m ⁻³	Ultrasonic velocity (C) ms ⁻¹	β × 10 ¹⁰ m ² × N ⁻¹	L _t (ρm)	Specific acoustic impedance Z × 10 ⁻³ kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	R × 10 ⁸ m ³ (m ³ s) ^{1/2}	$\frac{W}{\rho} \left(\frac{N}{m^3} \right)^{1/2}$
Benzene							
0.100	0.877 4	1 248 8	7.908 4	39.99	1 096	989	1 853
0.200	0.891 8	1 249.9	7.178 0	39.63	1 115	1 005	1 888
0.300	0.907 0	1 250 8	7 046 9	39.36	1 135	1 020	1 921
0.400	0.922 3	1 251.5	6 922 5	38.92	1 154	1 036	1 955
0.500	0.937 3	1 253.3	6.792 0	38.55	1 175	1 052	1 992
0.600	0.954 6	1 254.0	6.661 7	38.18	1 197	1 071	2 032
Butan-1-ol							
0.004	0.799 3	1 208.0	8.645 0	43.49	962	986	1 828
0.008	0.799 9	1 203.6	8.628 8	43.45	969	987	1 829
0.020	0.802 0	1 204.9	8.589 3	43.35	966	989	1 833
0.040	0.805 3	1 207.2	8.521 0	43.18	972	996	1 848
0.060	0.808 5	1 209.5	8.455 6	43.01	978	1 002	1 859
0.090	0.811 5	1 211.9	8.390 8	42.85	983	1 008	1 871
Acetone							
0.020	0.776 3	1 113.7	10.384 0	47.66	865	780	1 446
0.040	0.780 3	1 115.3	10.304 3	47.48	870	781	1 451
0.060	0.784 2	1 116.9	10.221 9	47.29	876	785	1 456
0.080	0.788 2	1 118.3	10.141 7	47.11	882	787	1 460
0.100	0.792 1	1 120.0	10.014 1	46.81	887	790	1 468
0.120	0.796 1	1 121.5	9.998 7	46.74	893	792	1 473

The adiabatic compressibility (β) of a solution is calculated using equation (1),

$$\beta = \frac{1}{C^2 \rho} \quad (1)$$

The adiabatic compressibility (Table 1) increases with decrease in concentration and rise in temperature. The apparent molar compressibility (φ_k) of the solution is calculated by using equation (2),

$$\phi_k = \frac{1000 (\beta \rho_0 - \beta_0 \rho)}{\rho \rho_0} + \frac{\beta M}{\rho} \quad (2)$$

where, M is the molecular weight of the solute, ρ₀ and β₀ are density and compressibility of the solvent, respectively. The calculated values of φ_k have been plotted against concentration (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Plots of apparent molar compressibility vs concentration of DDT solutions in butan-1-ol at different temperatures.

These values of φ_k decrease linearly with the increase in concentration at different temperatures and are best fitted to equation (3),

$$\phi_k = \phi_k^0 + S_k C \quad (3)$$

where, φ_k⁰ is the apparent molal compressibility at infinite dilution and S_k is the experimental slope. The values of the slope are negative (Table 2) which

TABLE 2—VALUES OF φ_k⁰ AND S_k FOR DDT SOLUTIONS IN ORGANIC SOLVENTS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Solvents	φ _k ⁰ × 10 ¹⁰			
	35°	40°	45°	50°
Benzene	2.96	3.24	3.50	3.62
Butan-1-ol	3.84	3.95	4.10	4.25
Acetone	4.76	5.02	5.32	5.62
	-S _k × 10 ¹¹			
Benzene	1.85	2.05	2.30	2.35
Butan-1-ol	3.33	3.67	3.90	3.88
Acetone	1.12	1.17	1.30	1.37

increase in different solvents with the rise of temperature. The values of φ_k⁰ also increase with the increase in temperature and vary in different solvents as benzene < butan-1-ol < acetone.

Intermolecular free length (L_t) has been calculated by using the semi-empirical relation⁹,

$$L_t = K^{-1/2} \beta^{+1/2} \quad (4)$$

where, K is a temperature dependent constant. The value of L_t decreases with increase in temperature. However, these values decrease slightly but linearly with increase in concentration. Acoustic impedance of the medium (Z) is calculated from the formula, Z = Cρ₀ for different types of wave motion present,

The acoustic impedance for the pesticides is found to increase linearly with increase in temperature. The value of Z varies in different solvents in the order, acetone < butan-1-ol < benzene. Molar sound velocity (R) and molar sound compressibility (W) have been calculated as using equations (5) and (6), respectively,

$$R = \left[\frac{M}{\rho} \right] C^{1/3} \quad (5)$$

$$W = \left[\frac{M}{\rho} \right] \beta^{-1/3} \quad (6)$$

where, M is the average molecular weight of the solution, calculated from the relation,

$$M = X_1 M_1 + X_2 M_2$$

where, X_1 and X_2 are the mole fractions of the solute and the solvent, and M_1 and M_2 are their respective molecular weights. Both the parameters increase linearly with the increase in concentration. However, these parameters do not vary much with the increase in temperature in benzene and butan-1-ol.

The adiabatic compressibility data have been used to calculate the solvation number (n_s) of DDT by using Passynky's relation¹⁰,

$$n_s = \frac{n_1}{n_2} \left[1 - \frac{V\beta}{n_1 V_1^0 \beta_0} \right] \quad (7)$$

where, V is the volume of solution containing n_2 moles of the solute and V_1^0 is the value of solvent. The values of n_s thus calculated, have the general trend of decrease with concentration non-linearly. However, it decreases slightly with temperature. There is no appreciable change of n_s value in different solvents.

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